

THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 2.5D ANGLE-INTERLOCK WOVEN SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Thermo-mechanical properties of 2.5D woven angle-interlock shape memory polymer composites with different weaving densities are investigated in the study. The thermo-viscoelastic constitutive relationship of the yarn is described in the form of hereditary integral. The parameters of relaxation moduli are obtained by nonlinear fitting of Prony series and finite element analysis.

Figure 1: Finite element model of 2.5D woven SMPCs ($N_t=6, N_p=11$).

It is shown that the relaxation moduli in three principle directions of woven composites increase with the increase of warp arranged density. With the increase of weft arranged density, the relaxation modulus in the warp direction decreases while the relaxation modulus in the weft direction increases.

(c)

 Figure 2: Effects of warp arranged density on the relaxation moduli of 2.5D woven SMPCs at 80°C. (a) E_x (b) E_y (c) E_z .

(a)

(b)

(c)

 Figure 3: Effects of weft arranged density on the relaxation moduli of 2.5D woven SMPCs at 80°C. (a) E_x (b) E_y (c) E_z .

In order to more intuitively reflect the effects of weaving densities on the viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs, the relaxation parameter R_I is defined as follows:

$$R_I = \frac{E_I(0) - E_I(\infty)}{E_I(0)} \quad (1)$$

where $E_I(0)$ and $E_I(\infty)$ represent the initial and asymptotic moduli along Direction I respectively. The value R_I directly reflects the magnitude of the viscoelastic effect of the woven composites in Direction I . Larger R_I corresponds to a stronger viscoelastic effect, and vice versa.

With the increase of warp arranged density, the viscoelasticity in the warp direction decreases. With the increase of weft arranged density, the viscoelasticity in the warp direction first increases until it reaches a maximum and then decreases.

Figure 4: Effects of warp arranged density on viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs.

Figure 5: Effects of weft arranged density on viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs.

Furthermore, two typical kinds of thermo-mechanical cycles are simulated based on the viscoelastic properties to investigate the shape memory behaviors of 2.5D woven SMPCs. The shape memory effects of SMPs or SMPCs are essentially due to the variation of viscoelastic properties as the temperature changes, and the shape fixation ratio and the stress recovery ratio can both be predicted from the relaxation parameters. The study in the paper proposes a feasible approach for further investigation of 2.5 woven SMPCs, and lays a foundation for their design and application in engineering.

Figure 6: Shape fixation ratios versus pre-deformed strains.

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